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Knowledge & Innovation stakeholders in the ERA FABRIC regions

Mapping regional/local stakeholders and communities
and needs analysis

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Executive Summary

The main purpose of this document is to show the **composition and characteristics of different types of existing and emerging stakeholders** in the ERA_FABRIC project partner regions within the 3 thematic domains addressed by the project: Sustainable manufacturing, Bio-based circular economy and Clean renewable energy.

In addition to the mapping of existing stakeholders, an **in-depth needs analysis** was performed in order to **identify current obstacles for the collaboration between different stakeholders** within and among the regions. Furthermore, **suggestions for improvement of the collaborations** and **skills needed** to support existing ones and establish new ones were also identified.

This mapping document will serve as a pool for the creation of the ERA FABRIC thematic working groups which, during the project duration, are expected to provide an overview on the forms of regional collaborations on the development of knowledge & innovation, obstacles hindering such cooperation, suggestions for the improvement and what is needed, in a form of institutionalized incentives and policies, to enhance quality of regional knowledge and innovation ecosystems.

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The list of stakeholders includes the entities that are the most relevant for this ERA FABRIC mapping exercise. There might be other entities, that operate in the project regions, that are not included, but might be considered in the project implementation.

Abbreviations

ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GVA	Gross Value Added
HE	Higher Education
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
K&I	Knowledge and Innovation
MS	Member States
RDA	Regional Development Agency
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
PR	Private
P	Public
PP	Public-Private stakeholders

Introduction

ERA FABRIC in a nutshell

The ERA FABRIC project is to implement a new ERA Hubs concept (COM 2020 628 final) across different geographies and structures in Europe, based on common compliance criteria. The process acts as an **incentive for advanced ecosystems to seek recognition, and for less advanced ecosystems to reach the criteria** facilitating support from European, national and regional level. Overarching aim of the ERA FABRIC project is to **define, structure, populate and validate the “interconnected knowledge space”** foreseen by the EU ERA Hubs initiative.

Three distinct, and intertwined, dimensions, all of them relevant for policy making, are adopted as a structuring principle for the community to be built and cultivated during the project:

1. ERA Hubs as **Knowledge Ecosystems** which foster the dynamic interaction of R&D and innovation actors at regional and multiregional levels, considering the different knowledge and cultural contexts and the alignment of research foci and industrial needs;
2. ERA Hubs as **Multi Stakeholder Platforms** which bring together the representatives of the various involved interest groups in a seamless and uninterrupted discussion and deliberation on strategic priorities, actions and results evaluation;
3. ERA Hubs as a **Policy Co Creation Toolbox** which are a transformative set of measures and tools operating in a “middle ground” needing to be configured as a distinct space from both the EU and the MS (member states) / regional levels, historically presided over by “ad hoc” sets of instruments (e.g. Framework Programmes for R&I, Structural and Investment Funds, Interregional and Cross Border Cooperation Programmes).

It is the consortium’s vision and assumption that the three above dimensions should be presided over and made interoperable, in order for the ERA Hubs initiative to become path breaking and impactful at broad EU level. ERA FABRIC is designed by leading European actors in the domain of regional development. The 11 partners represent 8 Member States and 1 Associated State. With the addition of the letters of interest gathered before the proposal presentation, almost half of EU27 territorial coverage will be reached.

Introduction

The purpose of the mapping

The main objective of the mapping is shedding light on the composition and characteristics of **different types of existing and emerging stakeholders from the Quintuple helix**, including their communities and networks in the project partner locations. Mapping keeps the distinction among the three thematic domains targeted by the ERA FABRIC project, namely:

**SUSTAINABLE
MANUFACTURING**

**BIO-BASED
CIRCULAR ECONOMY**

**CLEAN RENEWABLE
ENERGY**

This mapping document will serve as a **pool for the creation of thematic working groups** which during the project will provide an **overview on the forms of regional collaborations** on the development of knowledge & innovation, obstacles hindering such cooperation, suggestions for the improvement and, what is needed, in a form of institutionalized incentives and policies, to enhance quality of regional K&I ecosystem.

Geographic scope of the mapping covers 9 regions included in the project consortium Lower Austria, Jadranska Hrvatska, Jihovzchod, Emilia Romagna, Mazowieckie, Norte, Nord-West Romania, Cataluña and in 8 European countries (Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain).

This mapping is supported by an in-depth needs analysis aimed at highlighting the challenges associated with grasping the potential of available knowledge flows and transforming them into opportunities for growth and jobs. Such analysis has been carried out as a result of the first discussions within the afore-mentioned working groups.

Figure 1. Map of the Member States included in the ERA FABRIC consortium

Methodology

The mapping was performed through desk research to identify the main stakeholder groups as well as their role in their respective ecosystem and to gather initial information including contact details and a short description. In case some of the data was not available via the stakeholder website, an additional email or a phone call was made to gather missing information. Publicly available databases and directories, industry associations, research institutions, industry reports and publications, government statistics and reports, social media and online platforms, together with existing partner networks were used as a source of information.

Firstly, the types of stakeholders that are the subject of the mapping were identified and defined in groups and subgroups. Stakeholders that actively contribute to the knowledge and innovation ecosystems, together with those creating policies affecting R&D, implementing R&D activities, or having dedicated departments for R&D were included in the mapping. Selected stakeholders were **categorized by their “role in the ecosystem”** within one of the following Quintuple helix categories:

Policy makers

Government and public agencies that shape laws, regulations, and policies that affect knowledge and innovation.

Academia

Universities, research institutions and other educational organizations that generate new knowledge and develop the human capital necessary to drive innovation.

Industry representatives

Private sector companies, entrepreneurs and investors who develop and commercialize new products and services, creating economic value from knowledge and innovation.

Civil Society

Community organizations, NGOs and other groups that represent the interests of citizens and promote social and environmental responsibility.

Methodology

Since classification by the stakeholders' role in the ecosystem – academy, industry, policy makers, civil society – is very broad and does not provide sufficient clarity on the , scope of work and the type of the support that the stakeholder provides and variety of existing stakeholders types existing, following segmentation was introduced:

Clusters / professional associations

Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)

National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils

Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies

Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces

Regional Offices of in-line Ministries responsible for Innovation /
Management Authorities or Intermediate

Bodies for Innovation related programmes

Business support infrastructures

(logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)

Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations

Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and
Technology Parks

Business angels and venture investment companies

Sustainable development associations

Higher education institutions

Research institutes

Research centers

Methodology

Based on the baseline desk research, two additional categories were added, taking into consideration the differences between the ERA FABRIC regions and importance of the above-mentioned stakeholders for the functioning of the regional innovation ecosystems.

Based on the **legal status**, each stakeholder was grouped into the following categories:

Considering **stakeholders' level of influence, interest, and potential impact on the ecosystem** they were categorized in the three groups (A, B, C) based on the following criteria:

Methodology

Needs analysis methodology

Needs analysis related to the challenges associated with grasping the potential of available knowledge flows and transforming them into opportunities for growth and jobs within the three project domains was the second part of the mapping process. Focus group discussions were implemented in each partner region to gather input for an in-depth needs analysis.

Focus groups' organization

Each participating region provided an analysis of its respective region elaborated as a result of a focus group activity. The focus groups were set out including all relevant typology of stakeholders, selected from the performed mapping.

The main objective of the focus group was to obtain views and opinions, as clear and honest as possible, from all relevant stakeholder groups. Therefore, two needs were pondered: the creation of an environment where participants felt relaxed and were able to express their opinions at any moment, along with the balance in the participation of all participants, so that no one could get too much of the time in their interventions while others remained silent throughout the session.

Each focus group had one moderator experienced in similar activities and one rapporteur using a collaborative online tool to draft the main outputs and conclusions. The activity started with a self-presentation of the moderator and the presentation of the ERA FABRIC project and the activity itself. The moderator asked for the participants' permission to record the meeting for minutes and transcripts purposes. Once the main questions had been answered, the event was closed with a final section where all participants got the opportunity to pose their own questions and suggestions to improve relations and cooperation between all involved in the K&I ecosystems. Furthermore, after the final round of suggestions, the rapporteur shared the Miro board visualizing the discussed topics overall as well as main conclusions.

Focus groups were organized between May 28th and September 14th, 2023. Focus groups were held in the national languages while final conclusions were provided in English. The whole conversation was recorded for reference and future analysis. All participants of the focus groups signed informed consent before participating in the focus groups.

Topics discussed in focus groups

To explore the needs of each region and to be able to compare respective regions and identify similarities, common challenges, opportunities for mutual improvements and possibilities for collaboration, **the following questions were discussed:**

- How do you collaborate with other organizations in your region on developing regional knowledge and innovation ecosystems? Which challenges have you faced in the process?
- What are the main obstacles your organization faces when developing regional knowledge and innovation partnerships?
- Have you noticed any knowledge or skill gaps within your organization that are obstructing you from taking advantage of existing collaborations and knowledge flows? How might those skills help you to be more integrated in the regional ecosystem?
- Can you pinpoint possible opportunities for growth and job creation which you have noticed through collaborations, projects, or networks related to sustainable manufacturing, bio-based circular economy, and clean renewable energy?
- Do you have any specific policy or incentive in mind which would enhance the transfer of knowledge and expertise between regional stakeholders and the organization? What do you find necessary for the development of an innovation ecosystem?
- What do you see as an indicator of a well-functioning knowledge ecosystem?

Presentation of the results of the needs analysis

Information gathered via focus group discussion was analyzed qualitatively and is presented as narrative conclusions across four main axes of discussion for each of the participating regions:

- **Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships**
- **Ideas for improvement**
- **Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow**
- **Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation**

Furthermore, **visual conclusions with overlapping issues and ideas** across the different regions are presented as a final part of this mapping document.

Mapping by the region

Austria: Lower Austria

Baseline information

Lower Austria as a region surrounds the metropolitan region of Vienna and is dominated by heterogeneity of densely populated bacon-belt / industrial areas vs. sparsely populated rural areas, "shadowed by Vienna" with a high concentration of research education institutions and other relevant stakeholders with higher levels of importance.

In order to build up its own unique selling proposition for research, technology and innovation, Lower Austria has fostered **innovation ecosystems such as technopoles, clusters and platforms** over the last 20 years. The 4 existing clusters (Green Building, Food, Plastics, Mechatronics) strengthen the innovation capacity of companies, mainly SMEs, all over the region through collaborative innovation activities.

The 4 technopoles connect higher education, research and business on site at 4 technology locations addressing specific technology niches: center for biobased technology in Tulln, center for bioenergy, agricultural and food technology in Wieselburg, center for medical and material technology in Wiener Neustadt and center for health technology in Krems.

Mapping overview

Total of 25 stakeholders were identified across the Quintuple helix system in Lower Austria

- Academia
- Civil society
- Industry representatives
- Policy makers

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified in the Lower Austria region according to their role in the ecosystem

Figure 3. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in Lower Austria region (* 2 research institutes are characterized by mixed ownership)

Out of **25** stakeholders, **10** belong to academia, **8** are industry representatives, while **7** of them are policy makers. No representatives of civil society stakeholders were detected during the mapping process

- The mapping of industry representatives in Lower Austria was focused on bio-based circular economy (7 of them with the exception of 1 stakeholder who belongs to sustainable manufacturing).
- On the other hand, academia and policy makers are showing a tendency to be spread across all three domains.
- Majority of academic stakeholders cover bio based circular economy, 11 covers clean renewable energy and 2 of them fits into all three thematic domains.
- Significant number of policy makers (5 of them) belong to all three domains, while 1 covers bio based circular economy and 1 covers clean renewable energy

- Policy makers are entirely public entities (7 out of 7), while academia stakeholders follow the same pattern (8 public institutions) with the exception of having two institutions which are in joint public-private ownership

Public

Private

Public/Private

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Here are presented stakeholder mapped in Lower Austria region based on their role in the knowledge and innovation ecosystem as well as their importance for the provision and support to the R&D activities of the region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH - Center for Health & Bioresources	Bio-based circular economy	Research center	B
BLT Wieselburg - HBLFA Francisco Josephinum	Bio-based circular economy	Research center	A
Institut für Kulturtechnik und Bodenwasserhaushalt	Bio-based circular economy	Research center	B
University of Applied Sciences Wiener Neustadt - Campus Wieselburg	Bio-based circular economy	Higher education institution	A
University of Applied Sciences Wiener Neustadt am Campus Tulln	Bio-based circular economy	Higher education institution	B
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Institute for Environmental Biotechnology	Bio-based circular economy	Higher education institution	B
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Institute of Environmental Biotechnology	Bio-based circular economy	Higher education institution	B
BEST GmbH, Area Biorefineries	Clean renewable energy	Research center	A
BEST GmbH, Area Sustainable Supply and Value Cycles	All	Research center	A
Francisco Josephinum Research	All	Research center	B

Table 1. Mapped representatives of the academia in the Lower Austria region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Agrana Bioethanol GmbH	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
AGRANA Research & Innovation Center GmbH	Bio-based circular economy	Research center	B
Agrobiogel	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Farmdok GmbH	Bio-based circular economy	Research center	B
Lignovations GmbH	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Seiringer Umweltservice	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Veggie-Ponik Forschungs GmbH	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Hanfwelt Riegler-Nurscher	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B

Table 2. Mapped representatives of industry in Lower Austria region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Ecoplus. The Business Agency of Lower Austria, Technopol Tulln	Bio-based circular economy	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Ecoplus. The Business Agency of Lower Austria, Technopol Wieselburg	Clean renewable energy	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Accent Gründerservice GmbH	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
Ecoplus. The Business Agency of Lower Austria, Platform Bioeconomy	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Regional Government of Lower Austria, Department Economy	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Regional Government of Lower Austria, Department Science	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Tecnet equity NÖ Technologiebeteiligungs-Invest GmbH	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A

Table 3. Mapped representatives of policy makers in the Lower Austria region.

Mapping by the region

Croatia: Jadranska Hrvatska

Baseline information

Adriatic Croatia is composed of seven counties as a main type of functional and administrative units within the region. Due to the **centralized nature of Croatian governmental framework**, regional innovation ecosystems of Adriatic Croatia are strongly embodied into and dependent on the national innovation ecosystem.

At the regional level, research and innovation is coordinated through the network of Counties, Regional Development Agencies, Local Development Agencies and network of Chambers of Commerce for each respective county.

In accordance with the Law on Regional Development, Regional Development Agencies (functioning on the County level) are in charge of creation and implementation of County Development Strategy. On the City level, local authorities are expected to create and implement City Development Plans.

National strategic documents, Smart Specialization Strategy and Innovation Promotion Strategy, and Recovery and Resilience Plan, stipulate tailored incentives and actions for the encouragement of regional development since there are significant differences between Croatian regions, even within the Adriatic Croatia.

Mapping overview

Figure 4. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified in the Jadranska Hrvatska region according to their role in the ecosystem

Out of **81** stakeholders, **11** belong to academia, **42** are industry representatives, while **28** of them are policy makers. there were no representatives of the civil society identified in the mapping process.

- No significant differences were identified among the thematic domains, as the majority of stakeholders cover all 3 of them.
- The only category of stakeholders which is segmented over thematic domains are Industry representatives: while 22 of them cover all of the aforementioned domains, 1 industry rep-representative belongs to bio-based circular economy, 5 of them cover clean renewable energy and 14 stakeholders are based upon sustainable manufacturing.

Figure 5. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in Jadranska Hrvatska according to the role in the ecosystem, type of stakeholders and public, private ownership

- Industry representatives are the only category which shows tendency to be predominantly private owned, since almost 80% of the subjects are privately owned
- Academia and policy makers are exclusively public entities which are region-specific and nation-wide specific in the case of Jadranska Hrvatska and Croatia itself

Private

63.7%	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	21
18.2%	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	6
12.1%	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	4
3%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	1
3%	Clusters/ professional associations	1
TOTAL		33

Public

22.9%	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	11
12.5%	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	6
12.5%	Higher education institution	6
12.5%	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	6
10.4%	Research institute	5
10.4%	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	5
6.2%	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	3
4.2%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	2
4.2%	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	2
4.2%	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	2
TOTAL		48

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Here are stakeholder mapped in the region of the Jadranska Hrvatska presented based on their role in the knowledge and innovation ecosystem as well as their importance for the provision and support to the R&D activities of the region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Institute for Adriatic Corps and Karst Reclamation	All	Research institute	A
Institute of Agriculture and Tourism	All	Research institute	B
Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries	All	Research institute	A
Institute Ruđer Bošković - Martinska	All	Research institute	B
Juraj Dobrića University of Pula	All	Higher education institution	A
MEDILS - Mediterranean Institute for Life Sciences	All	Research institute	A
Polytechnic of Šibenik	All	Higher education institution	B
University of Dubrovnik	All	Higher education institution	A
University of Rijeka	All	Higher education institution	A
University of Split	All	Higher education institution	A
University of Zadar	All	Higher education institution	A

Table 4. Mapped representatives of the academia in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Zeleni Grad Šibenik	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Atos	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Energo	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Ericsson Nikola Tesla	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Include	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Sintaksa	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
AD Plastik	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Aluflexpack Novi d.o.o.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Calucem - Calcium Aluminate Cement factory	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Cromaris	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Development Innovation Center AluTech	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
HsTec	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A

Table 5. Mapped representatives of industry in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
KALI TUNA	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
LTH Metal Cast d.o.o.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Maritime Center for Electronics Ltd	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Omial Novi	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Rimac Automobili	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
ROTERM	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
SALONA VAR	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Sardina Postira	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Boomis ltd.	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
Business Accelerator Split	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
Business incubator Biograd na Moru	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
Cluster for eco-social innovation and development - CEDRA	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 5. Mapped representatives of industry in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Competence center Aktiva	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B
Competence center CEKOM 3LJ	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
E.C.H.R. Ltd.	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	B
Entrepreneurial center Scala	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	B
Entrepreneurial center Vrgorac	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations/Business Incubator	C
Entrepreneurial center Zovnica	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	C
Info Bip	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Innovative Zadar Ltd.	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B
Jadran-galenski laboratorij	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Lama Solutions4Business	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Manas/Statim	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Maritime Center of Excellence (MCoE)	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A

Table 5. Mapped representatives of industry in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Mosaic incubator ltd.	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
OIKON Ltd. – Institute of Applied Ecology	All	Research institute	B
PODI INDUSTRIAL ZONE - ŠIBENIK	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Start-up Rijeka	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	B
Synergia consulting	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	C
Technological Center Split	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B

Table 5. Mapped representatives of industry in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Blue European Digital Innovation Hub	All	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	B
Business incubator Klis	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B
Center for education and development Poličnik	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	A
Croatian Chamber of Commerce -County Chamber Split	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	B
Development agency Matica	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
Development Agency of Ličko-senjska County	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
Development agency Split - Rast	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
DUNEA ltd.	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
DURA ltd.	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
EDIH Adria	All	European Digital Innovation Hub	A
Entrepreneurial center Dubrovnik	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	C
Entrepreneurial center Split	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	A

Table 6. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
ICT Županija	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
Istarska County	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Kastelara	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	C
Lasta	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
Lika-Senj County	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Makarska development agency MARA	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
Plora ltd.	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
Primorsko-goranska County	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Public Institution RERA for the Coordination and Development of the Split-Dalmatian county	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
STEP-RI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Split-Dalmatia County	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Šibenik-Knin County Development Agency	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A

Table 6. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Šibensko-kninska County	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Trokut Center	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	B
ZADRA NOVA Agency	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	B
Zadar County	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 6. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Jadranska Hrvatska region

Mapping by the region

Czech Republic: South Moravia

Baseline information

The South Moravian Region has an advantageous position **on the main transportation arteries** toward two capital cities in surrounding states: Bratislava and Vienna. The region has large internal differences in terms of economic performance and situations in local job markets. Its performance is driven by the economic power of Brno (the capital city of the region) and its metropolitan region.

Brno, with its 381,000 inhabitants, represents the nation's second most important economic and knowledge centre. The region contains six additional regional population centres (Blansko, Břeclav, Hodonín, Vyškov, Znojmo, and Veselí nad Moravou) and five economically and socially disadvantaged territories (Znojmo, Moravský Krumlov, Hodonín, Kyjov, and Veselí nad Moravou).

Brno is home to all universities and nearly all other publicly funded research institutes are located in the region. Also, most companies in general and those investing heavily into research and development are situated in Brno.

South Moravian Region is **the most research-intensive region in the Czech Republic** with 3.2% share of expenses on R&D out of the region's GDP, thus also exceeding the capital Prague. In 2019, the population's level of economic activity remained just slightly below the national average, as did its average wage level. The GDP per capita (PPP based) remained at 96.9% of the national level, and 87.7% of the level for the EU28 (with a year-to-year change of 3.5 percentage points (p.p.)). Its 2018 GDP output represented 10.8% of the nation's output, which nearly corresponded with the region's share of the population (11.2%). Despite the region's agricultural and industrial tradition, these sectors lost ground to the rising service sector. In the share of services in the generation of gross value added (GVA—64.1%), the region placed second among the regions, just behind Prague.

Mapping overview

Figure 6. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified in the South Moravia region according to the role in the ecosystem.

Out of 47 stakeholders, 12 belong to the academia, 3 are representatives of the civil society, 27 are industry representatives, while 5 of them are policy makers.

- There is noticeable difference among coverage of thematic domains for two groups of stakeholders: academia and industry representatives.
- When put in numbers, academic stakeholders are spread as follows: 3 of them cover sustainable manufacturing, 2 represent bio-based circular economy, 1 belongs to clean renewable energy, 1 is a mix between sustainable manufacturing and clean renewable energy, while 5 of them are based upon all three domains.
- Industry representatives are following a similar pattern: 7 belong to sustainable manufacturing, 2 are built upon bio-based circular economy, 5 are covering clean renewable energy, 4 are mix between sustainable manufacturing and bio-based circular economy, 2 are combining sustainable manufacturing and clean renewable energy, while 7 of them, due to the range of their activities, belong to all three domains.

Figure 7. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in South Moravia region

- Academic, civil society and policy makers are exclusively public entities which is region-specific and nation-wide specific in the case of the South Moravia region and Czech Republic itself.
- Industry representatives is the only category which is almost entirely being privately owned (26 out of 27).

Private

100%	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	26
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TOTAL		26
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Public

35%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	7
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20%	Higher education institution	4
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20%	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	4
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10%	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	2
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10%	Sustainable development association	2
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5%	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	1
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TOTAL		20
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Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
CzechGlobe	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	B
CzPPN	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	B
CVVOZE - Centre for Research and Utilization of Renewable Energy	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	C
CEPLANT	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	B
CIISB - electron microscopy	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	B
NETME centre	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	B
CzechNanoLab	Sustainable manufacturing, clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Park	B
Brno University of Technology - Tech Transfer Office	All	Higher education institution	A
Masaryk University - Tech Transfer Office	All	Higher education institution	A
Mendel University - Tech Transfer Office	All	Higher education institution	B
University of Veterinary Sciences Brno	All	Higher education institution	C

Table 7. Mapped representatives of the academia in South Moravia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Forsage.net s.r.o.	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
Labdeers s.r.o.	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
ARBO Technologies, s.r.o.	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
ConWe s.r.o.	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
IN - EKO TEAM s.r.o.	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	-
Reair Systems s.r.o.	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
SIEMENS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	A
3Deposition s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
4dot Mechatronic Systems s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
CleverFarm, a.s.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
Honeywell	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	A
LIKO-S, a.s.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B

Table 8. Mapped representatives of the industry in South Moravia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Mevery	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
PSI (Photon Systems Instruments), spol. s r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
Affini Creative s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing, bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
Enantis s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing, bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
Myco s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing, bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
TIERRA VERDE s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing, bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
Fosfa a.s.	Sustainable manufacturing, clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
PROPASIV s.r.o.	Sustainable manufacturing, clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
2050farm s.r.o.	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
Centrum pasivního domu	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	B
Intemac Solutions	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	A
LESCUS Cetkovice, s.r.o.	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C

Table 8. Mapped representatives of the industry in South Moravia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Regionální hospodářská komora	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	A
Via Alta a.s.	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C
World from Space s.r.o.	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	C

Table 8. Mapped representatives of the industry in South Moravia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
City of Brno	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Czechinvest	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
JIC	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
JINAG	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
South Moravian Region	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 9. Mapped representatives of the civil society in South Moravia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
JCMM	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Nadace Partnerství	All	Sustainable development association	A
Nadace Veronica	All	Sustainable development association	B

Table 10. Mapped representatives of the policy makers in South Moravia region

Mapping by the region

Italy: Emilia Romagna

Baseline information

At the heart of the Emilia-Romagna innovation ecosystem lies a **large number of public and private actors who invest their resources and collaborate** in the exploitation of research results, new knowledge development, adoption of new technologies and innovation across all economic and social sectors.

In particular, the role of Emilia-Romagna's universities and research centres is crucial for development of the production system: knowledge, research and innovation are key factors for economic and production development in this region, where expertise and the diffusion of knowledge ensure competitiveness of the regional economic system in the face of change, with enhancement of regional areas of specialisation on the world market and concurrent consolidation of native production sectors within the territory.

The regional university system is composed of the universities of Bologna, Modena and Reggio Emilia, Ferrara and Parma, with decentralised campuses in the other main cities. In addition, Piacenza is home to the private Catholic University and Milan Polytechnic. Besides academic institutions, the Emilia-Romagna innovation ecosystem is characterized by the **several network and cluster organizations gathering together the vast majority of the relevant stakeholders**. The most important ones are the Emilia-Romagna High Technology Network, the Technopoles, the Clust-ERs and the recent ECOSISTER network.

The **Emilia-Romagna High-Technology Network** is composed of 89 Industrial research laboratories and 15 Innovation centres operating in the following fields: agri-food, construction, energy and environment, ICT and design, life science, mechanics and materials. Most of the laboratories are hosted within the Technopoles: 11 infrastructures located throughout the territory that stem from an initiative of the Region in collaboration with ART-ER, universities, research centres and local authorities. They organise activities and services for industrial research, technology transfer and for the development of high skills and careers on innovation.

Mapping by the region

Italy: Emilia Romagna

Baseline information

The **Clust-ERs** are associations of public and private bodies: companies, research centres and training institutions that share skills, ideas and resources to support the competitiveness of the industrial system in Emilia-Romagna. The Emilia-Romagna Region has found in the Clust-ERs the subjects capable of multiplying innovation opportunities through a collaborative approach, as they focus their activity in R&D strategic sectors: Agrifood, Building and Constructions, Cultural and Creative Industries, Energy and Sustainable Development, Health and Wellbeing, Mechatronics and Motoristics, Service Innovation, Tourism, Urban economy.

Together with the **Technopoles** and the High Technology Network laboratories, they are one of the key players in the regional innovation ecosystem coordinated by ART-ER, the Emilia-Romagna consortium for innovation and technology transfer. In that context, the competitiveness in the region no longer relies on the ability of individual research centres or businesses to operate on the global market, but increasingly on the ability of the entire local system to be innovative and attractive, in order to multiply opportunities and develop strategic projects and partnerships.

In addition to the Clust-ERs and High-Technology Network there is also the **Ecosister** project including a strong network of 23 public-private partners and 110 million euros of NextGenerationEU funding. Ecosister project integrates with the existing innovation ecosystem in the region (universities, research institutions, laboratories, and innovation centres) to support the productive system of Emilia-Romagna towards a sustainable transition. Ecosister promotes research activities on innovative materials for sustainable ecological transition; clean energy production, storage, and conservation; green manufacturing for a sustainable economy; intelligent solutions for mobility, housing, and carbon-neutral energy; circular economy and blue economy; ecological transition based on high-performance computing and data technology.

ART-ER coordinates Ecosister's Technology Transfer Innovation Programme (TTIP), which aims to promote industrial research as the main driver for sustainable economic development. The TTIP provides opportunities for all actors in the regional innovation ecosystem - university students and PhD candidates, researchers, innovative startups and research spin-offs, SMEs, companies, civil society organisations, and citizens, as well as the Public Administration - to contribute to the dissemination of green solutions, making the Emilia-Romagna region more sustainable, inclusive, and attractive.

Mapping overview

Figure 8. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholders identified in Emilia-Romagna region according to their role in the ecosystem

Out of **81** stakeholders, **34** belong to academia, **38** are industry representatives, **2** of them are policy makers, while **7** of them belong to civil society

- The highest number of academic stakeholders concentrated around clean renewable energy (14 in total), followed by sustainable manufacturing with 9 representatives, bio-based circular economy (6 stakeholders) and 5 stakeholders who are covering all three thematic domains
- Out of 2 policy makers representatives, 1 covers all three thematic domains, while 1 fit into the clean renewable energy domain. Civil society representatives are equally distributed among clean renewable energy (3 representatives) and those covering all three thematic domains (3 entities), while 1 belongs to bio-based circular economy

Figure 9. Graphic representation of the main stakeholders identified in the Emilia – Romagna region

- Academia is the only stakeholder which is predominantly in public ownership (27 public entities versus 7 private ones).
- Industry representatives are mainly privately owned (34 private representatives) while 4 of them are characterized by public ownership
- Policy makers are civil society representatives following the same pattern: there are 2 publicly owned policy maker entities and 1 privately owned, while there are 4 public civil society representatives and 2 private entities.

Private

50%	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	22
22.5%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	10
16%	Clusters/ professional associations	7
4.5%	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	2
4.5%	Sustainable development associations	2
2.5%	Sustainable development associations	1
TOTAL		44

Public

70.3%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	26
5.4%	Sustainable development associations	2
5.4%	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	2
5.4%	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	2
5.4%	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	2
5.4%	Clusters/ professional associations	2
2.7%	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	1
TOTAL		37

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
BIOGEST SITEIA - Centro Interdipartimentale per il Miglioramento e la Valorizzazione delle Risorse Biologiche	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CIPACK – Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca per il Packaging	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CIRI AGROALIMENTARE -Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca Industriale Agroalimentare	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CRPA LAB	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CRPV LAB	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Mister Smart Innovation ScrI	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
CertiMaC S.c.a r.L.	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CICCREI - Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca per la Conservazione, la Costruzione e la Rigenerazione di Edifici e Infrastrutture	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
CIDEA - CENTRO INTERDIPARTIMENTALE PER L'ENERGIA E L'AMBIENTE	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CIRI E&C- Centro di ricerca industriale di edilizia e costruzioni	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CIRI FRAME- Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca Industriale Fonti Rinnovabili, Ambiente, Mare ed Energia	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CMCC- Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A

Table 11. Mapped representatives of academia in Emilia - Romagna region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
CNR STEMS_FE - Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie per l'Energia e la Mobilità Sostenibili	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
CROSS TEC -LABORATORIO ENEA per l'Interoperabilità e virtualizzazione dei processi per reti di imprese	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Ecosister	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
EN&TECH - Centro Interdipartimentale per la Ricerca Industriale ed il Trasferimento Tecnologico nel Settore delle Tecnologie Integrate per la Ricerca Sostenibile, della Conversione Efficiente dell'Energia, l'Efficienza Energetica degli Edifici, l'Illuminazione e la Domotica	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
H2 Mo.Re. - Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca e per i Servizi nel settore della produzione, stoccaggio ed utilizzo dell'Idrogeno	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
L.E.A.P. Laboratorio Energia Ambiente Piacenza	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
LAERTE-LABORATORIO ENEA per l'Efficienza energetica e la sicurezza	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
LEA -LABORATORIO ENEA PER L'AMBIENTE	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Proambiente S.C.r.l.	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CENTRO CERAMICO- Consorzio Universitario per la Gestione del Centro di Ricerca e Sperimentazione per l'Industria Ceramica	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
CIRI AEROSPACE -Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca Industriale Aerospazio-Aerospace	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B

Table 11. Mapped representatives of academia in Emilia - Romagna region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
CIRI MAM - Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca Industriale Meccanica Avanzata e Materiali	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
CNR- ISSMC Istituto di Scienza, Tecnologia e Sostenibilità per lo Sviluppo dei Materiali Ceramici	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
DIGITAL AUTOMATION LAB REGGIO EMILIA	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
ENEA - Laboratorio Tecnologie dei Materiali Faenza	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
FONDAZIONE DEMOCENTER-SIPE	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
MechLav Laboratorio per la Meccanica Avanzata	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
CIFLA - Centro per l'innovazione tecnologica e sociale	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Università degli Studi di Ferrara	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Università degli Studi di Parma	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B

Table 11. Mapped representatives of academia in Emilia - Romagna region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Fondazione Raul Gardini	Bio-based circular economy	Sustainable development association	C
ANCI Emilia-Romagna	Clean renewable energy	Sustainable development association	B
ARPAE	Clean renewable energy	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Unione Nazionale Comuni Comunità Enti Montani Emilia-Romagna	Clean renewable energy	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	B
Federconsumatori ER	If other, indicate	Sustainable development association	A
Forum Terzo Settore Emilia-Romagna	All	Sustainable development association	A

Table 12. Mapped representatives of civil society in Emilia - Romagna region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Barilla	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Biosphere S.r.l.	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
CAVIRO	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Clust-ER Agrifood	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 13. Mapped representatives of industry in Emilia - Romagna region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Conad	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Conserve Italia	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Coop Alleanza 3.0	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Ecoinnovazione srl	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Micoperi BlueGrowth	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Orogel	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Sfridoo	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Biotec Sys S.r.l.	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
C.I.S.E - Centro per l'Innovazione e lo Sviluppo Economico -	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	C
Clust-ER Greentech	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
CRIT Srl	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Gruppo HERA	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A

Table 13. Mapped representatives of industry in Emilia - Romagna region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
ILLUMIA	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
IREN Group	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Rekeep	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Tampieri Holding	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
BI-REX - Big Data Innovation & Research Excellence	Sustainable manufacturing	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	B
Clust-ER Innovate	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Clust-ER Mech	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
DAMAS	Sustainable manufacturing	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	A
EGICON R&S	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
ER2Digit	Sustainable manufacturing	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	B
Fondazione REI	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
GHEPI S.r.l.	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C

Table 13. Mapped representatives of industry in Emilia - Romagna region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
I-NEST	Sustainable manufacturing	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	A
IMA Group	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Romagna Tech S.c.p.a	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
SACMI Group	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
T3LAB	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CERR- Confindustria Emilia-Romagna Ricerca	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Clust-ER Create	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
CNA INNOVAZIONE	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Tetra Pak Packaging Solutions S.P.A.	All	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Unioncamere Emilia-Romagna	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 13. Mapped representatives of industry in Emilia - Romagna region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
AESS - Agenzia per l'Energia e per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile	Clean renewable energy	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
ART-ER	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Regione Emilia-Romagna	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 14. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Emilia – Romagna region

Mapping by the region

Norway: Trøndelag

Baseline information

Trøndelag, as a region in Norway, plays a significant role in the Norwegian ecosystem for innovation. Situated in the heart of Norway, Trøndelag is known for its **strong industrial heritage, academic excellence, and active participation in research and development**. The focus on sustainability and regional development is clearly stated in the county's regional strategy for Trøndelag (Regional strategy for value creation in Trøndelag 2022-2025) and therefore strongly supports the broader commitment to sustainable growth throughout Norway.

Trøndelag is home to some of Norway's leading academic and research institutions, including the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) and SINTEF, the largest independent research organization in Scandinavia. These actors participate in numerous research and development projects, both on a national and international level. Working closely together with industries all over Norway, these institutes foster cutting-edge research and innovation that provides a valuable foundation for innovation and technology development in fields such as renewable energy, health, and sustainable technologies within the maritime sector.

Trøndelag also has **several strong industrial clusters, incubators, and innovation hubs** that actively participate in national and international collaborative networks to provide a nurturing environment for start-ups, entrepreneurs, and SMEs. The headquarters of Investinor – a publicly owned VC that manages Norwegian's state interests in seed capital and pre-seed funding schemes – are also located in Trondheim, rigged to co-invest with private investors to accelerate growth.

Overall, Trøndelag's active participation in the Norwegian ecosystem for innovation makes it a crucial contributor to the country's technological advancements and economic growth

Mapping overview

Figure 10. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified in the Trøndelag region according to the role in the ecosystem.

Out of **111** stakeholders, **4** belong to academia, **105** are industry representatives, while **2** of them are policy makers. However, there were no civil society stakeholders detected during the mapping process

- No differences in stakeholder distribution were detected when it comes to policy makers as both of them cover all three thematic domains. Academic stakeholders cover mostly clean renewable energy with 50% (2 out of 4) in that sector, while one belongs to sustainable manufacturing and 1 fit into all three thematic domains
- Industry representatives are present across all three thematic domains: 69 of them belong to clean renewable energy, 14 cover bio-based economy, 6 are concentrated in sustainable manufacturing, and 1 fits into all three domains

Figure 11. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in the Trøndelag region

Private

75%	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	75
5%	Business support infrastructures (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	5
5%	Clusters/ professional associations	5
5%	Research center	5
4%	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	4
3%	Business angels and venture investment companies	3
3%	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	3
TOTAL		100

- Academia and policy makers are entirely publicly owned while, at the same time, industry representatives are entities privately owned (100 out of 105) with the exception of 2 subjects which are publicly owned

Public

36%	Higher education institution	4
36%	Regional Offices of in-line Ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	4
18%	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	2
10%	Business angels and venture investment companies	1
TOTAL		11

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
+CityxChange	Clean renewable energy	Higher education institution	A
NTNU Energy	Clean renewable energy	Higher education institution	A
NTNU Department of Manufacturing and Civil Engineering	Sustainable manufacturing	Higher education institution	A
NTNU	All	Higher education institution	A

Table 15. Mapped representatives of the academia in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Biokraft AS	Clean renewable energy	Higher education institution	A
Fiborgtangen Næringspark	Clean renewable energy	Higher education institution	B
Grønn Plattform Seaweed SINTEF	Sustainable manufacturing	Higher education institution	A
Grønn Plattform SirkAQ	All	Higher education institution	B

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Jordpro	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
NCE Aquatech	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Norske Skog Skogn	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO)	Bio-based circular economy	Research centre	A
Oceanize	Bio-based circular economy	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
SallMar	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
ScaleAQ	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D project	A
Sirkellaget	Bio-based circular economy	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Thamsklyngen	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Utoplast	Bio-based circular economy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Ægir Harvest AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Aitos Gasification Technology AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Alva Industries AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Aneo AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Aneo Build AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Aneo Energy AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Aneo Industry AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Aneo Mobility AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Aneo Real Estate AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Aneo Retail AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Biokraft AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
BNW-Energy AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Bryte AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Cadio AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
CTM Lyng AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Defa AS avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
DHI AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Dynavec AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Ei - Watch AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Elekt AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Enemite AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Enoco AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Enoco ITB AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
ENUAAS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Equinor Ventures	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Freyr Battery Norway AS avd Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Getek AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
GFMS AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Glen Dimplex Nordic AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Global Green Energy AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Greenfox Solutions AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Haf Power Solutions AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Hansen Technologies Norway AS avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Hark Technologies AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Hiltra Industripark og Kysthavn	Clean renewable energy	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Hydrogen Mem-Tech AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Hydroinformatikk AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
IC Technology AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Inrigo AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
ISI-Tech AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Kiona AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Kråkøya Biopark	Clean renewable energy	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	C
Luxsave AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Metertech AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Motkraft Gruppen AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Niras Norge AS Avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Ocean Energy AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Ocean Power Parks AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Piscada AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Rainpower Holding AS avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Renergy Cluster	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Rolls-Royce Electrical Norway AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Romy Klima AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Safebase AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Sedicon AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Sikom AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
SIMIS AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
SINTEF Energy	Clean renewable energy	Research centre	A
Skynordic AS avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Solarseek AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Sunlit Sea AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
The Switch Marine Drives Norway AS avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
TMAC AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Versiro AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Vestas Norway AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
VinGrip Energy AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Voith Hydro AS Avd. Trondheim	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Volue Technology AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	B
Winns AS	Clean renewable energy	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	C
Flokk AS	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Norbit	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Nordic Semiconductor AS	Sustainable manufacturing	Industry representatives having R&D departments or participating in R&D projects	A
Papirindustriens Forskningsinstitutt	Sustainable manufacturing	Research centre	A
SINTEF Manufacturing AS	Sustainable manufacturing	Research centre	A

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Wood-works Cluster	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
6AM	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
DIGS	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B
Faktry	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
Fremtidens Industri AS	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	A
Innovation Norway	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
Investinor	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Proneo	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	B
ProVenture	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Research Council of Norway	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
RFF Trøndelag	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
SIVA	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
T:lab	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
Tidligfasefondet	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B
Viking Venture	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	C
Work-Work	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	B

Table 16. Mapped representatives of the industry in Trøndelag region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Trøndelag County Authority	Sustainable manufacturing	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Trondheim Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 17. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Trøndelag region

Mapping by the region

Poland: Mazowieckie

Baseline information

Mazowieckie Voivodeship includes two NUTS II regions. The Warsaw Capital Region is the leader in almost all innovation rankings in Poland. **The Mazovia Regional, opposite to the capital one, usually tends towards the bottom of these rankings.** At EU level, according to the European Innovation Scoreboard 2023, Warsaw Capital Region is labeled as Moderate innovator and Mazovia Regional is in the group of Emerging innovators.

Mazovia has a great economic potential. More than 850.000 economic entities operate in the region, but the vast majority of which are concentrated in the Warsaw Capital Region, particularly in the city of Warsaw (more than 70% of the region's entities). Approx. 1% of all Mazovian companies are hi-tech entities, and 36% are entities of the knowledge-based services sector. Approximately 24% of the total number of companies in Mazovia are active in the field of innovation. Among them, 24.2% of industrial companies and 18% of service companies collaborated with others on innovation activities in 2017-2019. This percentage is strongly differentiated by the size of the company – the larger the company, the greater the propensity to enter into the cooperation on innovation. Such cooperation was undertaken by 33.1% of large industrial enterprises and only 2.1% of small enterprises¹.

According to the above report the innovation ecosystem includes: research entities (137), higher education institutions (89), business supporting organisations (60) and clusters (9). Unfortunately, from the perspective of much balanced regional sustainable development, the vast majority of research entities and higher education institutions are based in Warsaw. Development disparities in the area of innovativeness are a natural consequence of the poorer socio-economic situation of municipalities of the Mazovia Regional in comparison to those of the Warsaw Capital Region. This concerns such areas as: the level of local entrepreneurship, unemployment, average gross salary, share of inhabitants with higher education or availability of educational services. As a consequence, there are fewer companies in the Mazovia Regional, including innovative ones. In both regions, **the lack of innovation needs** is the main reason for not implementing or developing innovations.

¹ Adopted from Raport Końcowy: Analiza wąskich gardeł innowacji, w tym cyfryzacji na Mazowszu, Warsaw, 2022, <https://innowacyjni.mazovia.pl/upload/pages/2352/2352-0.pdf> and Regional Innovation Strategy for Mazovia 2030: <https://innowacyjni.mazovia.pl/download/2381/>

Mapping by the region

Poland: Mazowieckie

Baseline information

The main barriers to the diffusion of innovation in terms of knowledge transfer to the economy are poor supply of knowledge from the science sector to the economy, low effectiveness of intermediaries in the exchange of knowledge between the science sector and the economy, weak demand for knowledge in the economy, poor supply of knowledge suitable for commercialisation, developmental disproportions between the two regions in Mazovia.

Enterprises are more willing to cooperate in carrying out innovative activities with other companies (40% of companies have undertaken such cooperation) than with scientific institutions (20% of companies) and business supporting organisations (9%). For companies undertaking cooperation with the scientific sector, the most frequently selected partners are the Warsaw-based Warsaw universities like Warsaw University of Technology, Warsaw University of Life Sciences, Warsaw University of Technology, and Warsaw University.

The collaboration between companies and other actors in the innovation ecosystem is established **mainly through personal relationships**. This is particularly important when establishing cooperation with research institutions – their structure and procedures make it difficult for companies to reach the right person. The initiators of cooperation are primarily companies. Research units rarely reach out to entrepreneurs with their offer. Only 18% of companies cooperating with the sector declare that, in their case, it was an academic unit that proposed cooperation to them. A small percentage of companies use the services of Business Supporting Organisations, which is largely due to unfamiliarity with their offer, or even lack of awareness of their existence.

Mapping overview

Total of 110 stakeholders across the Quintuple helix system were identified in Mazowieckie region

- Academia
- Civil society
- Industry representatives
- Policy makers

Figure 12. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified Mazowieckie region according to the role in the ecosystem

Out of **110** stakeholders, **11** belong to the academia, **9** are representatives of the civil society, **74** are industry representatives, while **16** of them are policy makers.

- No significant differences were identified among the thematic domains as the majority of stakeholders cover all 3 of them.
- The only category of stakeholders which shows tendency to be distributed across different thematic domains are industry representatives: while 54 of them cover all of the afore-mentioned domains, 3 industry representatives belong to bio-based circular economy, 7 of them cover clean renewable energy and 10 stakeholders are based upon sustainable manufacturing.

Figure 13. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in Mazowieckie region

Public

22%	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	6
18%	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	5
14%	Higher education institution	4
14%	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	4
11%	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	3
7%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	2
7%	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	2
3.5%	Research institute	1
3.5%	Clusters/ professional associations	1
TOTAL		28

- Academic stakeholders are mainly public entities (9 out of 11).
- Policy makers are entirely public entities (16 out of 16)
- There are only 2 Industry representatives characterized by the public ownership

- Industry representatives are the only category which is almost equally distributed between private and public-private types of ownership (39 versus 33), while 2 subjects are publicly owned.

Private

76%	Clusters/ professional associations	38
8%	Sustainable development associations	4
6%	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	3
6%	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	3
4%	Higher education institution	2
TOTAL		50

Private/Public

91%	Business angels and venture investment companies	29
6%	Business support infrastructures (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	2
3%	Clusters/ professional associations	1
TOTAL		32

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Here are presented stakeholder mapped in the region of the Mazowieckie based on their role in the knowledge and innovation ecosystem as well as their importance for the provision and support to the R&D activities of the region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Applied Research Institute – Warsaw Institute of Technology	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
INNOTECH4LIFE (Warsaw University of Life Science)	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	A
Kozminski University	All	Higher education institution	A
Łukasiewicz Research Network	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Pawel Wlodkowic University College in Plock	All	Higher education institution	A
Polish Academy of Science	All	Research institute	A
University of Warsaw	All	Higher education institution	A
UWRC sp. z o. o.	All	Higher education institution	B
Warsaw University of Life Science	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	A
Warsaw University of Technology	All	Higher education institution	A

Table 18. Mapped representatives of the academia in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
AgroBioCluster	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Food4Good	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Polish Federation of Food Manufacturers Employers' Association	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Black Swan Fund	Clean renewable energy	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Chamber of Commerce for Energy and Environmental Protection	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Chamber of Commerce Polish Heating Industry	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
EnerFund	Clean renewable energy	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Hydrogen Poland	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish Chamber of Energy Storage	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Smok Ventures	Clean renewable energy	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
APPLiA Association of Domestic Appliances Employers	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Chamber of Industry and Commerce of Scrap Management	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Employers' Association of the Packaging and Products Industries in Packaging EKO-PAK	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
KnowledgeHub	Sustainable manufacturing	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Movens Capital	Sustainable manufacturing	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Polish Chamber of Commerce of Furniture Manufacturers	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Radom Metal Cluster	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
SunFish Partners	Sustainable manufacturing	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
The Polish Chamber of Automotive Industry	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
The Polish Chamber of Packaging	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Aper Ventures	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Arkley Brinc VC	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Association for the Development of Entrepreneurship and Local Initiatives	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Atmos	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Avia Capital	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
bValue	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Radom Area	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Chamber of Commerce of the Ciechanów Subregion	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Chamber of Commerce of the Plock Subregion	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
CofounderZone	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
CogitoCapital	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
DigitalPoland Foundation	All	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	A
District Chamber of Commerce in Legionowo	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Eastern Chamber of Commerce	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
ECCVentures	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Employers of Poland	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
FOUNDATION FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Foundation for the Development of Polish Agriculture	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Freya Capital	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
FundingBox Deep Tech Fund	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Invento	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Kogito Venture	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Mazovian Chamber of Craft and Entrepreneurship	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Mazovian ICT Cluster	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Mazovian Science and Technology Park -Co-operative Park	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Montis Capital	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
MOST Foundation	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
National Chamber of Waste Management	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Netrx Ventures	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
NextRoad Ventures	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Pathfinder	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Plock Industrial and Technological Park	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Płoński Chamber of Commerce	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish Chamber of Chemical Industry	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish Chamber of Commerce for Electronics and Telecommunications	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish Chamber of Commerce for High Technology	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish Chamber of Electronic Communications	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish ESG Association	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Polish Institute for Research and Development	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Polish Technology Platform for Photonics	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
SCANDERIA VENTURE	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Science and Technology Park "Świerk"	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Simpact Ventures	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
SPINAKE ALFA	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
STARTUP ACADEMY	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	A
Startup Hub Poland	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
THE FOUNDATION FOR ENERGY CONSERVATION	All	Business support organization (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
«Twój StartUp» Foundation	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	B
UNIMOS Alliance	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
VC LINK	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Waste Management and Recycling Cluster - National Key Cluster	All	Clusters/ professional associations	A
Xplorer Fund	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Youth Business Poland	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, Co-working spaces	A
Zyrardow Association for Entrepreneurship Support	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B

Table 19. Mapped representatives of industry in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Chief Technical Organisation	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Chief Technical Organisation - Ciechanów branch	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Chief Technical Organisation - Ostrołęka branch	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Chief Technical Organisation - Płock branch	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Chief Technical Organisation - Radom branch	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Chief Technical Organisation - Siedlce branch	All	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Climate coalition	All	Sustainable development association	A
Green Mazovia	All	Sustainable development association	B
INNOWO	All	Sustainable development association	B

Table 20. Mapped representatives of civil society in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Mazovian Energy Agency	Clean renewable energy	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	B
City Hall of Warsaw	Sustainable manufacturing	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
Future Industry Platform	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
Industrial Development Agency	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Marshall Office of Mazovia Voivodeship	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Mazovia Development Agency	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Ministry of Climate and Environment	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Ministry of Economic Development and Technology	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Ministry of Science and Higher Education	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
National Centre for Research and Development	All	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
PFR Ventures	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A

Table 21. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Mazowieckie region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Polish Agency for Enterprise Development	Clean renewable energy	Regional Development Agencies/ Innovation Agencies	A
Polish Development Fund	Sustainable manufacturing	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
The Ministry of Funds and Regional Policy	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Voivodeship Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Warsaw	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 21. Mapped representatives of policy makers in Mazowieckie region

Mapping by the region

Portugal: Norte

Baseline information

The best way to analyze Norte region sectoral and thematic alignment of the institutions that make up the regional scientific and technological network is to associate them with the different priority domains of smart specialization of S3 NORTH 2027, namely: (i) Creativity, Fashion and Habitats; (ii) Sustainable Mobility and Energy Transition; (iii) Industrialization and Advanced Manufacturing Systems; (iv) Agro-environmental Systems and Food; (v) Life Sciences and Health; (vi) Territorial Assets and Tourism Services; (vii) Resources and Blue Economy; (viii) Technologies, State, Economy and Society.

Global data allows us to conclude that all priority domains of smart specialization are associated with regional scientific and technological institutions. However, the relative concentration is not indifferent in this analysis, as it can be observed that the highest number of institutions are associated with four domains: Sustainable Mobility and Energy Transition; Industrialization and Advanced Manufacturing Systems; Agro-environmental Systems and Food; Life Sciences and Health. On the other hand, the domain of Territorial Assets and Tourism Services is the one with the least associations, perhaps due to having fewer resources and knowledge and technology-intensive assets.

The regional innovation system (RIS) of the Norte region implies **autonomous governance models capable of generating necessary interactions among relevant stakeholders**, particularly in entrepreneurial discovery processes. The governance model of RIS establishes, for the first time, the creation of the Regional Innovation Council of the North (CRIN) as an advisory body aimed at ensuring active participation of regional actors in monitoring and continuous evaluation of strategy implementation and contributing to the strategic decision-making process. This advisory body adheres to the quadruple helix model, involving representatives from companies, educational and research institutions, public planning and management entities for R&D&I policies, and innovation users or entities representing the demand and consumers of innovation.

Overall, in the Norte Region there are 57 organisations that can be considered technology infrastructures according to the National Innovation Agency. They range from Technology and Innovation Centres to diverse types of Research and tech transfer units, science and technology parks and S&T incubators.

Mapping by the region

Portugal: Norte

Baseline information

At the heart of the vision for Europe is the goal of leadership in technology, innovation and economic competitiveness, which is why the development of strategies linked to Research and Innovation has been increasingly evident, favouring the same smart specialisation within territories' competences and opportunities framework. In Portugal, Innovation and Competitiveness increasingly arise from interactions between economic and non-economic agents, where infrastructures, resources and skills are brought together to develop new solutions in national and international demand.

Technology and Innovation Centres (CTIs) are entities dedicated to the production, dissemination and transmission of knowledge, aimed at companies and economic value creation, contributing to the pursuit of public policy objectives, within the framework of priority specialization areas, whether national or of the regions in which they operate.

Collaborative Laboratories (CoLabs)

Collaborative Laboratories (CoLABs) are entities dedicated to the production, dissemination and transmission of knowledge by pursuing their own research and innovation agendas. Based on a portfolio of products or systems with higher added value, CoLABs aim to facilitate the access of companies to global markets through exports, as well as to support the attraction of foreign investment in technology-intensive areas. CoLABs can be national, regional/local, or entrepreneurial, steering their activities to the creation of qualified employment and economic and social value in the intermediate space of the innovation system. The Norte region of Portugal hosts 15 CoLABs (for detail, see mapping of entities in the North Region).

Mapping overview

Figure 14. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified in the Norte region according to their role in the ecosystem.

Out of 57 stakeholders, 16 belong to academia, 40 are industry representatives, while 1 of them is policy maker. There were no civil society representatives identified in the mapping process.

- Academic stakeholders mostly cover all three thematic domains with the exception of 3 entities which belong to bio-based circular economy and one which covers sustainable manufacturing
- Industry representatives are most notably spread between io-based circular economy (16 stakeholders) and sustainable manufacturing (14 stakeholders). The rest of them either belong to all three thematic domains (16 stakeholders) or to smaller extent to clean renewable energy (3 stakeholders)

Figure 15. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in Norte region

- Academia is mostly a public entity (12 out of 16 stakeholders), same as policy makers.
- Industry representatives are into greater extent publicly owned (24 public versus 12 privately owned stakeholders)

Private

Public

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Here are presented stakeholder mapped in the Norte region based on their role in the knowledge and innovation ecosystem as well as their importance for the provision and support to the R&D activities of the region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
I3S Associated Laboratory	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Inov4Agro Associated Laboratory	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
LABELS Associated Laboratory	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
INEGI Instituto de Ciência e Inovação em Engenharia Mecânica e Engenharia Industrial - CTI	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CCG Centro de Computação Gráfica - CTI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Centro ALGORITMI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
INESC TEC Associated Laboratory & CTI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
INL International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Instituto Politécnico de Bragança	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C

Table 22. Mapped representatives of the academia in the Norte region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Instituto Politécnico do Cávado e Ave	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Instituto Politécnico do Porto	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Universidade Católica Portuguesa	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Universidade do Minho	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Universidade do Porto	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B

Table 22. Mapped representatives of the academia in the Norte region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Cluster da Vinha e do Vinho	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Cluster do Mar Português	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Cluster Smart Cities Portugal	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	B
COLAB 4LIFELAB	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C

Table 23. Mapped representatives of the industry in the Norte region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
COLAB AQUAVALOR	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB B2E	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB FORESTWISE	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
COLAB MORE	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB NET4CO2	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB VINES AND WINES	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB4FOOD	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CVR Centro para a Valorização de Resíduos - CTI	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
DIH 4 Climate Neutrality	Bio-based circular economy	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	C
DIH Fórum Oceano	Bio-based circular economy	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	B
Health Cluster Portugal	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	C
Portuguese AgroFood Cluster	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ professional associations	C

Table 23. Mapped representatives of the industry in the Norte region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
COLAB BIOREF	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB CEIIA - S2UL	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB VGCOLAB	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CATIM Centro de Apoio Tecnológico à Indústria Metalomecânica - CTI	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CITEVE Centro Tecnológico das Indústrias Têxtil e do Vestuário de Portugal - CTI	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Cluster Automóvel Portugal	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	C
Cluster da Plataforma Ferroviária Portuguesa	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	C
Cluster do Calçado e Moda	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	B
Cluster Têxtil: Tecnologia e Moda	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	B
COLAB BUILT COLAB	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CTCP Centro Tecnológico do Calçado de Portugal - CTI	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
DATA COLAB	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B

Table 23. Mapped representatives of the industry in the Norte region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Digi4Fashion	Clean renewable energy	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	C
DIH 4 Global Automotive	Clean renewable energy	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	C
PIEP Associação Pólo de Inovação em Engenharia de Polímeros - CTI	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
PRODUTECH - Pólo das Tecnologias de Produção	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ professional associations	B
PRODUTECH DIH	Sustainable manufacturing	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	B
ATTRACT DIH	All	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	A
CEiIA Centro de Engenharia e Desenvolvimento - CTI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CENTITVC Centro de Nanotecnologia e Materiais Técnicos, Funcionais e Inteligentes - CTI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB DTX	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB PROCHILD	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
COLAB VORTEX	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
IEP Instituto Electrotécnico Português - CTI	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CCDR Norte		National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 23. Mapped representatives of the industry in the Norte region.

Mapping by the region

Romania: Nord – Vest

Baseline information

Romania has **8 development regions** at NUTS2 level, which have **no legal and administrative status**, but play an important role in the implementation of the Cohesion Policy programmes and regional statistics. They were established in 1998 by the regional development law, currently updated by Law no.315/2004.

At the regional level, in Romania there is **no regional innovation policy authority**. The support of innovation at regional level is justified by the strategic and programming documents developed at the local and regional level. In each development region is functioning one regional development agency (RDA), which is a non-governmental and non-profit body of public utility, with legal personality, operating in the field of regional development.

The RDAs are responsible for coordinating the design and implementation of regional development strategies and plans, being the executive bodies of the corresponding Regional Development Councils, composed of appointed elected mayors and county council presidents. In the previous programming period, the RDAs acted as Intermediate Bodies for the ROP 2014-2020 and currently are Managing Authorities for the eight regional-level Regional Programmes in 2021-2027. Within the EU Cohesion Policy, for the first time in Romania, starting from 2021, the Regional Programmes are different for each of the 8 regions and are managed by the regional development agencies as Management Authorities.

From governmental funds, the multi-annual programmes for SMEs development, competitiveness & innovation capacity, launched by the Ministry of the Economy, are implemented by 8 regional offices of the Agency for SMEs and Export Promotion.

Mapping overview

Total of 99 stakeholders across the Quintuple helix system were identified in Nord Vest region

- Academia
- Civil society
- Industry representatives
- Policy makers

Figure 12. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified Mazowieckie region according to the role in the ecosystem

Out of **99** stakeholders, **19** belong to academia, **5** are representatives of the civil society, **61** are industry representatives, while **14** of them are policy makers

- No differences were detected among the thematic domains as 100% of those stakeholders cover all 3 of them
- Academia and industry representatives are distributed across all three thematic domains while there are also representatives which cover all three domains. The largest part of academic entities covers all 3 domains (34 of them), while the rest is spread between sustainable manufacturing (5 representatives), bio-based circular economy (4 representatives) and clean renewable energy (2 representatives). Industry representatives predominantly cover all three domains (34 entities) and sustainable manufacturing (22 entities), while a smaller share belongs to bio-based circular economy (2 entities) and clean renewable energy (3 entities)
- Industry representatives are predominantly privately owned (55 out of 61 representatives), while 3 are publicly owned and 3 representatives are characterized by mixed private-public ownership
- Civil society representatives are mainly privately owned (3 entities), while 2 of them are in mixed private-public ownership

Figure 16. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in Nord Vest region

- Industry representatives are predominantly privately owned (55 out of 61 representatives), while 3 are publicly owned and 3 representatives are characterized by mixed private-public ownership
- Civil society representatives are mainly privately owned (3 entities), while 2 of them are in mixed private-public ownership

Private

37%	Business support infrastructures (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	22
26%	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	15
15%	Clusters/ Professional associations	9
12%	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	7
6%	Business angels and venture investment companies	4
2%	Research Institute	1
2%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	1
TOTAL		59

Public

37%	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	13
34%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	12
23%	Higher education institution	8
3%	Regional Development Agency/ Innovation Agencies	1
3%	Research Institute	1
TOTAL		35

Public/Private

40%	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	2
40%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	2
20%	Business Accelerator/ Startup support organizations	1
TOTAL		5

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Here are presented stakeholder mapped in the Nord Vest region based on their role in the knowledge and innovation ecosystem as well as their importance for the provision and support to the R&D activities of the region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Babe -Bolyai University (UBB)	Bio-based circular economy	Higher education institution	B
Oradea CNCG-CTT	Bio-based circular economy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Research Institute for Analytical Instrumentation (ICIA)	Bio-based circular economy	Research centre	B
The University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca (USAMV)	Bio-based circular economy	Higher education institution	B
CENTI Technological Transfer Center	Clean renewable energy	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
University of Oradea	Clean renewable energy	Higher education institution	B
CIT TEHNOINF BN	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
CIT-UTCN-CUNBM	Sustainable manufacturing	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Technical Science Academy of Romania (ASTR) - Cluj subsidiary	Sustainable manufacturing	Higher education institution	B
The Institute of Interdisciplinary Research in Bio-Nano-Sciences	Sustainable manufacturing	Higher education institution	B

Table 25. Mapped representatives of the academia in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
THE ROMANIAN ACADEMY Cluj subsidiary	Sustainable manufacturing	Higher education institution	B
Academy of the Scientist from Romania	All	Higher education institution	B
CRPPI-PATLIB CLUJ	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
INCDTIM Cluj-Napoca	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
IPA	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
Romanian Institute of Science and Technology (RIST)	All	Research centre	B
Technological Transfer Centre of INCDTIM Cluj-Napoca	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
The Technical University of Cluj-Napoca	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	B
The Tehnical University of Cluj-Napoca (UTCN)	All	Higher education institution	B

Table 25. Mapped representatives of the academia in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Cluj Cowork	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
Cluj Hub	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
DIH4Society	All	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	C
Ixperiment	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	C
Transilvania Digital Innovation Hub (TDIH)	All	Digital Innovation Hubs (regional and those that are part of the EDIH network)	C

Table 26. Mapped representatives of the Civil society in the Nord Vest region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
AgroTransilvania Cluster (ATC)	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
Transylvania LifeStyle Cluster	Bio-based circular economy	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
Eco-innovative Cluster for a sustainable environment (CLEMS)	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
KPMG Startup Grow Pad	Clean renewable energy	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
Transylvania Energy Cluster	Clean renewable energy	Clusters/ Professional associations	C

Table 27. Mapped representatives of industry in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Eurobusiness Oradea IV	If other, indicate	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
ARC Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Aries Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Business Park Bistrița South (BPBS)	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Câmpia Turzii Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Cluj Innovation Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Eurobusiness Oradea III	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Industrial Park Săcueni	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Jibou Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
MG TEC Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Nervia I	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Nervia II	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A

Table 27. Mapped representatives of industry in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Nord Carei Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Romanian New Materials Cluster (RNMC)	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
Schwaben Business Park Petrești	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Space Tech Cluster	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
Tâmășeu Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Tetarom I	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Tetarom II	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Tetarom III	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Tileagd Industrial Park	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Transylvanian Furniture Cluster	Sustainable manufacturing	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
West Park Oradea	Sustainable manufacturing	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
ABC Incubator	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	A

Table 27. Mapped representatives of industry in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Activize TECH	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
Bihor Scientific and Technological Park	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Cluj IT Cluster	All	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
Cluj Startups	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
CRPPI-PATLIB BIHOR	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CRPPI-PATLIB BISTRIȚA-NĂȘĂUD	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
CRPPI-PATLIB MARAMUREȘ	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	C
Eurobusiness Oradea I	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Eurobusiness Oradea II	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Fortech Investments	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Future Makers	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Innovation Labs	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A

Table 27. Mapped representatives of industry in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Liberty Technology Park	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
MakeITinOradea	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	A
MakeITinOradea	All	Clusters/ Professional associations	A
Oradea Tech Hub	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
Oradea Tech Hub	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	A
RebelVentures	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Risky Business	All	Business Accelerator/ Startup support organizations	A
RO TSA (Romanian Tech Startups Association)	All	Business Accelerator/ Startup support organizations	A
Silicon Forest	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	C
Something Big	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Spherik Accelerator	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A
Startup Reaktor	All	Business Incubators, Hubs, co-working spaces	A

Table 27. Mapped representatives of industry in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
TETAPOLIS	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
TETAROM Incubator	All	Business Accelerator/ Startup support organizations	A
Transilvania IT Cluster	All	Clusters/ Professional associations	C
Transylvania Angels Network	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	A

Table 27. Mapped representatives of industry in the Nord Vest region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Baia Mare Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Bihor County Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Bistrița Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Bistrița Năsăud County Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Cluj County Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Cluj-Napoca Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 28. Mapped representatives of policy makers in the Nord Vest region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Maramureş County Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
North-West Regional Development Agency	All	Regional Development Agency/ Innovation Agencies	A
Oradea Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Sălaj County Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Satu Mare County Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Satu Mare Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Zalău Municipality	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A

Table 28. Mapped representatives of policy makers in the Nord Vest region.

Mapping by the region

Spain: Catalonia

Baseline information

Catalonia, as a region in northeastern Spain, boasts a diverse and vibrant knowledge and innovation ecosystem. It is known for its **unique blend of industrial strength and cultural heritage**, which has contributed to **its reputation as a hub for creativity and entrepreneurship**. One of the key features of Catalonia's knowledge and innovation ecosystem is its strong emphasis on research and education. The region is home to several prestigious universities and research institutions, including the University of Barcelona, Pompeu Fabra University, and the Catalonia Institute for Energy Research, among others. These institutions play a crucial role in fostering cutting-edge research and knowledge creation across various disciplines.

Catalonia has also developed a **network of innovation clusters and technological parks** to nurture collaboration and innovation among companies. These clusters focus on different sectors and areas of expertise, such as Information and Communication Technologies, Biotechnology, Renewable Energy, and Design. The clusters serve as platforms for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and the development of joint projects, enhancing the innovation capacity of companies operating in Catalonia.

In addition to the clusters, Catalonia has established **several technology parks and innovation centers strategically located throughout the region**. These parks serve as physical spaces where academia, research organizations, and businesses can coexist and collaborate. Furthermore, Catalonia has made significant investments in specialized centers that focus on specific technology niches. These centers bring together experts and resources to advance innovation in targeted areas.

Overall, Catalonia's knowledge and innovation ecosystem benefits from **its diverse industrial base, world-class research institutions, innovation clusters, technological parks, and specialized centers**. These elements combine to create a dynamic environment that fosters collaboration, entrepreneurship, and the continuous development of new ideas, positioning Catalonia as a leading region for research, technology, and innovation in Europe.

Mapping overview

Figure 17. Geographic distribution of the main stakeholder identified in the Catalonia region according to the role in the ecosystem

Out of **104** stakeholders, **34** belong to the academia, **1** is representative of the civil society, **52** are industry representatives, while **17** of them are policy makers

- No differences were detected in stakeholder distribution across thematic domains as the majority of stakeholders cover all 3 of them. There is only 1 policy maker stakeholder belonging to clean renewable energy and 1 civil society stakeholder covering sustainable manufacturing.

Figure 18. Graphic representation of the main stakeholder identified in Catalonia region

Private

Public

Private/Public

76%	Clusters/Professional associations	26
6%	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	2
6%	Research center	2
6%	Regional Offices of in-line Ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	2
3%	Business support infrastructures (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	1
3%	Higher education institutions	1
TOTAL		34

- Academy showcases all 3 varieties of the ownership type: private, public and mixed type of the ownership (private-public).
- Policy makers are almost exclusively public entities.
- Industry representatives are mostly private-public entities or private.

Overview of the mapped stakeholders by the role of the stakeholder

Here are presented stakeholder mapped in the Catalonia region based on their role in the knowledge and innovation ecosystem as well as their importance for the provision and support to the R&D activities of the region.

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Barcelona School of Economics - BSE	All	Higher education institution	C
Barcelona supercomputing center - national supercomputing center (BSC-CNS)	All	Research center	A
Catalan institute for water research (ICRA)	All	Research centre	B
Catalan institute of chemical research (ICIQ)	All	Research center	A
Catalan institute of nanoscience and nanotechnology (ICN2)	All	Research center	B
Center for ecological research and applied forestry (CREAF)	All	Research center	A
Center for genomic regulation (CRG)	All	Research center	B
Center for research in agricultural and food economics (CREDA)	All	Research center	C
Centre for research in agricultural genomics (CRAG)	All	Research center	B
Computer vision center (CVC)	All	Research center	B

Table 29. Mapped representatives of the academia in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Consortium for the construction, equipment and operation of the synchrotron light laboratory (CELLS-ALBA)	All	Research center	B
ESADE	All	Higher education institution	B
Eurecat	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Forest technology center of Catalonia (CTFC)	All	Research center	A
I2CAT Foundation, internet and digital innovation in Catalonia	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
IESE	All	Higher education institution	B
Institute for advanced architecture of Catalonia (IAAC)	All	Research center	B
Institute of agrifood research and technology (IRTA)	All	Research center	A
Institute of high energy physics (IFAE)	All	Research center	B
Institute of photonic sciences (ICFO)	All	Research center	B
International center for numerical methods in engineering (CIMNE)	All	Research center	B
IQS	All	Higher education institution	C

Table 29. Mapped representatives of the academia in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Leitat	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat de Barcelona	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat de Girona	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat de Lleida	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat Internacional de Catalunya - UIC	All	Higher education institution	B
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya - UOC	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat Pompeu Fabra	All	Higher education institution	A
Universitat Ramon Llull	All	Higher education institution	B
Universitat Rovira I Virgili	All	Higher education institution	A
Water technology center (Cetaqua)	All	Research center	A

Table 29. Mapped representatives of the academia in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
4Founders Capital	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
5GBarcelona	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
AEI INNOVI Association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
AMBIT Living spaces cluster	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Barça Innovation Hub (BIHUB)	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Barcelona Activa Incubators	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Barcelona Activa SA SPM	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Barcelona Leather cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Barcelona Science Park	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Bstartup	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Caixa Capital	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Catalan advanced materials cluster association, CLUSTERMAV	All	Clusters/Professional associations	B

Table 30. Mapped representatives of the industry in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Catalan association for innovation and internationalization in the water sector, CWP	All	Clusters/Professional associations	A
Catalan bioenergy cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	A
Catalan biotechnology and health tech company association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	B
Catalan Children's products cluster association, KID's cluster	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalan cluster association for the sports industry	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalan innovation association for the pork meat sector, INNOVACC	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalan textile and fashion group	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia AI DIH	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Catalonia audiovisual cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia automotive industry cluster - CIAC	All	Clusters/Professional associations	B
Catalonia beauty cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia digital cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	B

Table 30. Mapped representatives of the industry in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Catalonia Digital Innovation Hub (DIH4CAT)	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Catalonia Foodservice cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia gourmet cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia Illumination Cluster - CICAT	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia Machinery and Agriculture production means cluster - FEMAC	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Catalonia mental health cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Digital Farming Hub	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Digital Impulse Hub	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Digital Water Innovation Hub	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
EDUTECH Education technology promotion Cluster business association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
ESADE Creapolis	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Experience-based industries Hub (e!xperience)	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B

Table 30. Mapped representatives of the industry in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
IoT Catalan Alliance	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Itinig	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	B
La Salle Technova Barcelona	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Neàpolis	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Packaging cluster association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Parc agrobiotech Lleida	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	C
Parc tecnològic de Barcelona	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Parc tecnològic del Vallès - PTV	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	C
Plug and Play Tech Center	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
Rail group association	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Real estate services association cluster, CSIM	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
REIMAGINE Textile	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B

Table 30. Mapped representatives of the industry in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Seedrocket	All	Business Accelerators/ Startup support organizations	B
Southern European Cluster in photonics and optics - SECPHO	All	Clusters/Professional associations	C
Tecnocampus Technology Park	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	B
Catalonia efficient energy cluster - CEEC	ases	Clusters/Professional associations	A

Table 30. Mapped representatives of the industry in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Catalan institute of energy (ICAEN)	Clean renewable energy	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	B
ACCIÓ	All	Regional Development Agencies / Innovation agencies	A
Barcelona Activa	All	Regional Development Agencies / Innovation agencies	A
Barcelona City Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Barcelona institute of technology for the habitat - Bithabitat	All	Innovation and Tech transfer organizations, including Science and Technology Parks	A

Table 31. Mapped representatives of civil society in Catalonia region

Name of stakeholder	Thematic domain	Type of stakeholder	Level of importance
Barcelona metropolitan area (AMB)	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Barcelona Provincial Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Cambra de Comerç de Barcelona	All	Business support infrastructure (logistic parks, industrial parks, technology parks, industry platforms)	A
Catalan waste agency	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
Catalonia Trade & Investment	All	Regional Development Agencies / Innovation agencies	B
Foment del Treball	All	Regional Offices of in-line ministries responsible for Innovation / Management Authorities or Intermediate Bodies for Innovation related programmes	A
Generalitat de Catalunya	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	A
Girona Provincial Council	All	National/Regional/Local Governments/Municipalities, County councils	B
Lleida Provincial Council	All	Business angels and venture investment companies	B
PIMEC	All	Clusters/Professional associations	A
Tarragona Provincial Council	All	Clusters/Professional associations	B

Table 31. Mapped representatives of civil society in Catalonia region

Needs analysis results

Austria: Lower Austria

Focus group was organized on 30th of May. Overall 7 participants confirmed and participated in the event: 3 representatives from university and research organizations and 4 representatives of intermediary organizations including technopole manager, start-up incubator representative and technology transfer agency. The specificity of this focus group was that only two thematic domains were covered: biobased circular economy and clean renewable energy.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Ostosterreich region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- Lack of time and motivation from researchers for initiating cooperation with companies as they are mainly financed through basic research projects
- Lack of structures and funding instruments for cross-regional cooperation and difficulties in inclusion in pan European or pan regional cooperation (high competition and high administrative burden)
- Knowledge and infrastructure are available in the region but not efficiently used due to duplication and overlaps with no strategic coordination and collaboration of intermediaries in European projects and networks
- There are too many self-contained small networks in the region
- Insufficient market implementation of research results
- Career paths in science and business are separate from each other, researchers hardly found start-ups or switch to a position in private industry (and back to a job in research)
- Not enough funding for prototypes (TRL 6+)

Needs analysis results

Austria: Lower Austria

Ideas for improvement

- Better knowledge about competencies and capacities of potential partners in order to strengthen research capacity as a whole region
- Small basic non-competitive funding to support initiating cooperation and project development
- Better communication of benefits of cooperation in EU
- Incentives to facilitate the job change from science to business (and back)
- Incentives and more time for researchers to pay more attention to the exploitation and usability of research results in research projects (example innovation awards for researchers)

- Instruments to improve accessibility of research results for civil society to increase acceptance and relevance of research together with incentives for “crowd sourcing” of research questions and innovation idea
- Clear process and standard models how (and at what costs) to transfer IPR from university/research organization to founder in case of a spin-of/start-up
- Bring international investors to Austria
- Specific personnel in research institutions to facilitate spin-offs

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Improve (increase efforts in) science communication
- Realistic involvement of civil society

Needs analysis results

Croatia: Jadranska Hrvatska

Focus group was organized on the 19th of July. Overall 7 participants confirmed and participated in the event while 1 dropped out just before the start of the event: 2 representatives from the management of academic institutions, 2 representatives from the regional policy makers from two different counties, and 2 company representatives (one head of production and one head of the R&D unit).

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Jadranska Hrvatska region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- ▶ Sluggishness of the system and lack of the systemic top-down support
- ▶ Existing partnerships are established and dependent on the enthusiasm of individuals and their professional connections from prior collaborations
- ▶ Small & medium enterprises are not aware of the existing possibilities for cooperation
- ▶ No evaluation or incentive mechanism for researchers participating in collaborative projects with companies/industry

Ideas for improvement

- ▶ Creation of established system for attracting investors
- ▶ Promotion of best practices and success stories of existing collaborations between different stakeholders
- ▶ Organization of conferences and other networking events where representatives of different stakeholders have the opportunity to meet, exchange ideas and initiate collaboration
- ▶ Establishment of the industrial PhDs so young researchers are in contact with industry from the very beginning of their carriers

Needs analysis results

Croatia: Jadranska Hrvatska

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Transversal skills, such as project management and communication, are recognized as the key ones
- Recognition of research managers as a profession
- Recognized need to educate supporting and administrative staff to provide project support
- Change in mindset and attitudes towards collaboration in the K&I ecosystem
- Joint proof of concept laboratories or testbeds as a place for collaboration between different stakeholders

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Collaborations are predominantly project based and funded from publicly available funds
- Collaborations are based on the individual efforts of usually the same people

Needs analysis results

Czech Republic: South Moravia

Focus group was organized on 13th of June. Overall 8 participants confirmed and participated in the event: 1 representative from university and 1 from research organization, 1 representative of the public administration, 1 SME and 4 representatives of intermediary organisations including chambers of commerce, innovation agencies and clusters.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the South Moravia region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- Strategic priorities between universities/companies and city/region are not well aligned – implementing strategic (building) projects takes ages.
- Most activities are centered in the Brno and metropolitan region – this is perceived especially as a challenge by the public administration
- Low structuring of the supporting innovation ecosystem with overlapping roles and no “map” or guidance for companies where to ask for which advice
- Lack of capacity in the SMEs regarding the understanding and inclusion in innovation activities and lack of supporting structures for/within companies
- Universities expect added value from cooperating with companies, while companies have clear needs and sometimes want just an easy service.
- University budgets are tied with project funding – there is very little “free money” to develop own initiative projects with companies
- Mismatch between national and regional policies – good strategies on the regional level, while at the national level strategies are either missing or not being implemented
- There is no funding associated with the Regional Innovation Strategy – individual projects are funded from different funding sources (mainly on the national level)
- Cities and regions primarily support (financially) agencies that they have established and not other supporting actors

Needs analysis results

Czech Republic: South Moravia

Ideas for improvement

- Measures for greater mobility of people between the academia and business sector
- Improve communication towards the public so that it understands the added value of research and innovation
- Better targeted support for companies
- Networking among companies (start-ups, scale-ups or corporations) and the local research community
- Customized work with corporations on their research needs in a given research area
- Link the Regional Innovation strategy with appropriate funding

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Skills on how to transfer research ideas into businesses employment of relevant people as coordinators of collaboration.
- Innovative public procurement

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Measures for greater mobility of people between the academia and business sector
- Transfer of know-how from Brno to the less developed parts of the region. Intermediary instruments
- Funding of long-term systemic operators like South Moravian Innovation Centre or INTEMAC

Needs analysis results

Italy: Emilia Romagna

Focus group was organized on 13th of July. Overall 10 stakeholders confirmed and participated in the event: 3 representatives from regional clusters, 4 representatives of Ecositers hub spokes (coming from Academia), one representative of National research organization, one representative of national municipalities and one representative from the Third Sector Forum.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Emilia-Romagna region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- ▶ Lack of common ground for collaboration due to mismatch in interests or lack of trust
- ▶ Organisational and technical difficulties of smaller entities when it comes to the collaboration
- ▶ Universities struggling to establish long-term collaboration with companies
- ▶ Too many channels of collaboration, simplification is needed
- ▶ Too many channels of collaboration, simplification is needed
- ▶ Difficulties in dissemination of results as there are still industrial actors that are unaware of dedicated university services or do not know whom to approach
- ▶ Difficulties in the regulatory field, particularly in the transposition of European directives at the national level
- ▶ Remote areas have harder access to the opportunities and resources and are less connected

Needs analysis results

Italy: Emilia Romagna

Ideas for improvement

- Put in place strategic facilitators of the collaboration (i.e. CLUST-ERs) especially since their network and direct contact is wide
- Incentives for collaboration between industry and academia, especially for the companies lacking own R&D capacities
- Adjusting and reviewing policies to better fit needs of entire ecosystem
- Communicate needs and expectations at an early stage
- Launch of dedicated calls/programs to overcome bottlenecks and fostering a cohesive approach at local level
- Ensure resources to retain the best talents

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Technical skills are necessary, but also facilitation and social innovation skills in the territory for sustainable ecological transition
- Well-trained supporting staff members to boost research and innovation activities
- Improve Communication skills of researchers
- Reinforce the system of competence upskilling and reskilling in order to satisfy the job market demand

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Good capacity of interaction of the regional ecosystem, highly developed in terms of number of actors and opportunities to develop joint projects
- Public engagement must be taken into account in the development of an ecosystem

Needs analysis results

Norway: Trondelag

The focus group was organized on the 22nd of August. Overall 4 participants confirmed and participated in the event: 1 representative from the university, 1 representative from the municipality, and 2 representatives from intermediary organisations and clusters. The specificity of this focus group was that only two thematic domains were covered: biobased circular economy and clean renewable energy.

Overall, the following conclusion was reached for the Trondelag region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- Identifying relevant partners and getting in contact with them for projects
- Different expectations put into the project from different stakeholders and lack of common ground for collaboration
- Physical distance between partners is often an issue
- Slow absorption of research results into industry - researcher is moving fast, but the industry needs more time to implement new products
- Number of policy instruments (EU, national government, regional government) with lack of alignment

Ideas for improvement

- Better knowledge about competencies and capacities of potential partners in order to strengthen research capacity in the region
- Adjusting and reviewing policies to better fit needs of entire ecosystem
- Communicate needs and expectations at an early stage

Needs analysis results

Norway: Trondelag

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Negotiation skills
- Skills on emerging technologies (i.e. using new materials that are being created at a fast pace from other industries)

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Build better networks and understand other regional actor's needs and competencies
- The Research Council of Norway and Innovation Norway could be more transparent in advance of calls (like the EU does), so that applicants can give feedback

Needs analysis results

Poland: Mazowieckie

Focus group was organized on 27th of July. Overall 13 participants confirmed and participated in the event: 5 representatives of academic and research organisations, 3 of public authorities, 3 of chamber of commerce, 2 representatives from the business supporting organisations and one representative of regional agency and professional association.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Mazowieckie region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- Majority of industry representatives and companies do not see direct benefits from cooperation with regional authorities in local/ regional knowledge and innovation ecosystems
- Complicated (bureaucratic) and quite often limited accessibility in funding schemes and lack of permanent funding holding up collaboration
- A lack of common local/ regional collaborative platforms with available information about the R&I policy processes at local and regional level
- Legal obstacles and lack of flexibility limits involvement in some activities. Public bodies need to follow strict admin procedures to arrange formal activities and have very strict rules on how they can spend/ allocate funds
- Difficulties in approaching right stakeholders, particularly from peripheries of the Mazovia region

Needs analysis results

Poland: Mazowieckie

Ideas for improvement

- ▶ Improving communication within the ongoing collaborative activities with explaining better purposes, rules and potential benefits
- ▶ Identify any motivation from the company representatives that would engage them in collaboration
- ▶ Providing incentives to companies for participation in collaborative projects and ensuring clear communication of benefits from participation
- ▶ Increasing the awareness of public entities' procedures runtime duration
- ▶ Promotion of the success stories, specifically about the knowledge that transforms the linear model of economy into a network economy with a strong local/ regional dimension
- ▶ Employment of knowledgeable and experienced people as coordinators of collaboration

- ▶ Competence building and exchange of good practices in collaboration

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- ▶ Investing in entrepreneurial skills of the young generation
- ▶ Leadership

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- ▶ Instruments supporting soft skills development
- ▶ Moderation of collaborative activities matching capital region with peripheries by regional authorities
- ▶ Intermediary instruments to support collaboration

Needs analysis results

Portugal: Norte

Focus group was organized on 14 of September. Overall 15 participants confirmed and participated in the event: 2 representatives regional clusters and Digital Innovation Hubs, 3 representatives from universities, one representative of National Innovation Agency S3 expert, 2 representatives of Collaborative Laboratories, 4 representatives of CTI – Centers of Technology and Innovation and 2 representatives of industry.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Norte region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- ▶ Limited connection between the scientific and business system and low economic valuation of knowledge (e.g. patents)
- ▶ Low qualification of human resources and reduced investment in business R&D and innovation and salaries that are not competitive enough to attract and retain qualified human resources
- ▶ Imbalanced network of SRI institutions, with a clear division between low-density territories and the rest of the region
- ▶ Low technology intensity which results in low economic output
- ▶ Overwhelming majority of micro and small and medium-size companies (but with a tendency for clear growth in high-tech startups, spin-offs and tech upgrade in SMEs and large companies);
- ▶ Mismatch between academic and industrial timescales and methodologies

Needs analysis results

Portugal: Norte

Ideas for improvement

- Formalize and consolidate the Regional Innovation System (RIS) which would be capable of responding to the challenges of valorizing products and activities in the Norte region
- Align innovation support with the regional strategy, based on the governance model of the smart specialization regional strategy and a better coordination with the European Structural and Investment Funds.
- Promote and attract selective investment to enhance high value-added economic activities, with environmentally friendly technologies and products
- Increase public funding designed to support the integration of PhD researchers in industrial settings, joint projects that are high TRL oriented and focused on developing technology solutions, higher co-fund percentages for both R&I institutions
- Reinforce cluster-based approaches to collaboration and networking

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Continue developing distinctive knowledge in various fields of smart specialization aimed at enhancing economic and social activities, the provision of goods and services, and tangible and intangible heritage.
- Well trained Intellectual property specialists, business development specialists and communication specialists - cutting across the disciplinary boundaries
- Risk mindset and capacity to absorb and integrate innovative processes and technology
- Management skills
- Retain and attract individuals and enhance their multiple and irreplaceable talents, from creatives to entrepreneurs, in a context of continuous improvement of their educational and skill levels.

Needs analysis results

Romania: Nord Vest

Focus group was organized on 29h of June. Overall 41 participants (and 29 entities) confirmed and participated in the event: 4 representatives of public administration/municipalities, 3 representatives from regional development agency, 6 participants from universities and technology transfer offices, 9 from clusters, 6 from civil society, 6 from accelerators and incubators and 1 from financial institution and 6 from companies.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Nord Vest region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- ▶ Number of EU and nationally funded projects but no strategic approach and mutual collaboration between important stakeholders in the region
- ▶ Strong disparity between Cluj city and the rest of the 42 cities in the region, in terms innovation related activities and results Lack of private money (own money) of clusters and accelerators
- ▶ Strong disparity between urban and rural in terms of activities (both innovation and economic related)
- ▶ Companies difficult to engage in innovation related actions
- ▶ Except clusters (which represent a very small part of the companies in the region), there are no active business association to commit and also no business support authorities to engage them (chambers of commerce in Romania are NGOs , are not public entities and the membership is not mandatory – few companies are members of chambers
- ▶ Competition among the regional stakeholders and focus on individual growth rather than on collaborative instruments
Lack of trans-sectoral support

Needs analysis results

Romania: Nord Vest

Ideas for improvement

- Increase public support to startups
- A better synergy between planning projects & initiative among the regional stakeholders
- Better visibility of each others expertise together with the platform for promoting research outcomes and innovative demand
- Matchmaking sectors by connecting supply and demand of technology and innovative services and products
- Develop a network of HE project writing - by training staff in RTOs, companies and consultants
- Need for a common committed strategy for growth, in terms of innovation, to ensure complementarity of actions and intra-regional synergies

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Expertise for access to funding - only few organisations/ small teams have the capacity to write European projects (based in clusters, universities, regional development agency)
- Actions for capacity building and staff exchanged between organisations
- Lack of expertise in companies for project writing / consultancy companies not experiences in supporting HE project writing, merely focus on nationals ERDF calls

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Organization of working groups based on common interest fields, to constantly explore interests and opportunities
- Organization of info days for access to funding
- Organization of working session for project writing

Needs analysis results

Spain: Catalonia

Focus group was organized on 29th of June. Overall 8 participants confirmed and participated in the event: 2 representatives from university, 2 representatives from public administration, 1 representative of intermediary organization, one from clusters and one from SMEs and one from communication.

Overall, following conclusion was reached for the Catalonia region:

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

- The mismatch in project expectations from research institutions and private sector
 - Participation in tenders and lack of trust when it comes to the selection process and its transparency
 - Lack of communication and knowledge of the positive impact that cross-sectoral collaborations may have in society
 - Complex and time consuming bureaucratic process that hinders some actors from participation
 - There is a lack of entrepreneurship and culture of “fear”, and a lack of courage, about entrepreneurship.
- Certain companies (especially SMEs) do not have the necessary knowledge to have a meaningful participation in big tenders, especially European/international
 - The main problem in research is talent retention. It is almost impossible to compete with the private sector when there is such a big difference in salaries and in contract quality.
 - Misalignment of expectations between clients and technology providers due to the TRL system regarding the framework of a service provision
 - IPR conflicts in the process of transfer of knowledge, mainly when the co creation takes places in a project

As a positive side it was emphasized positive feedback when it comes to the procedures related to the management of IP and ecosystem provides tools and processes to manage it properly.

Needs analysis results

Spain: Catalonia

Ideas for improvement

- More resources and incentives to retain talent in universities and research centers in order to be able to compete with the private sector
- Creation of additional indicators in order to measure the innovation progress and degree in the region (i.e. creation of spin-offs, number of patents, rather than purely academic stuff such as scientific publications)
- Recognition of the orchestration role of regional administrations and acknowledgment of their profession and salaries in line with the responsibilities and amount of job.
- Emphasize the importance of co creation processes in the development and transfer of knowledge
- Improve the communication among agents to align project expectations

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

- Lack of competences of the people in organizations for an ecosystemic and holistic approach of the challenges to be tackled
- Improve knowledge of European tendering processes among SMEs

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

- Facilitate good practices, real examples and clarifications on general terms related to TRL system and IPR management in an easier and understandable way

Needs analysis results

Needs analysis conclusions

Focus group discussions and needs analysis showed that, although there are many differences in terms of state of the development of regional knowledge and innovation ecosystems of the ERA FABRIC regions, specifically in terms of number and type of stakeholders and their role in the ecosystems, as well as types of collaborations that are existing, we all share some common problems and obstacles when it comes to the collaboration.

The graph at Figure 20 presents common obstacles, ideas for improvement and types of the knowledge flows and collaboration foreseen that are common for all ERA FABRIC regions.

This map sets baseline info that will help ERA FABRIC consortium in creating and developing the next working groups activities and elaboration of policy recommendations but also to create ideas for the future events and activities that will serve as an example of change of knowledge and innovation ecosystem, creating better collaboration pathways and impact for society.

Needs analysis results

Graphic illustration of overlapping conclusions from the focus group discussions

Obstacles for establishing knowledge & innovation partnerships

Skills needed to enhance knowledge flow

100-0 Level of importance

Needs analysis results

Graphic illustration of overlapping conclusions from the focus group discussions

Ideas for improvement

Forms of collaborations on developing knowledge & innovation

100-0 Level of importance

Framing And Bridging Regional research and Innovation ecosystems Capacities for a renewed ERA – ERA FABRIC

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